

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACTS OF TOURISM: TRANSFORMATIONAL LEARNING THEORY

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ABSTRACT

Currently, in the development of international tourism in the countries of the world, great attention is paid to increasing the socio-economic importance of tourist enterprises. It is naturally becoming popular to actively contribute to the field of tourism, which has become one of the four priority sectors in the world, as much as possible, that is, to involve them on a large scale in the organization of various tourist services. Also, we should not forget the analysis of the results of such tourist activities. The socio-psychological impact of tourism can cause both positive and negative consequences.

Keywords: social psychology, behavior, tourism Impoacts , transformational learning.

INTRODUCTION

Social psychology is the science of examining and analyzing the behavior of an individual or group of people in different society. In other words, social psychology is a discipline that scientifically examines people’s opinions about other people and the way they interact with them [1]. The issue of research on the study of personality in the field of social psychology, especially the practical tasks in this regard, is being solved on the basis of the psychological and sociological approaches that are at the center of the science of social psychology. In addition, social psychology is also expressed as a field of science that tries to understand the nature and causes of individual behavior in social environments. In this sense, social psychology examines the individual and his/her environment and the social groups consisting of the group and its environment.

Tourism is a mind-opening experience that teaches people that the world does not consist of a single life model. There are other life models [2], because it is believed that tourism positively affects world peace. When people travel from place to place with a sincere desire to learn more about their global neighbors, their knowledge and

understanding increases. Thus, a start is made to develop world communication, which is very important in building bridges of mutual appreciation, respect, and friendship through tourism [3].

The tourism industry has been in the center of attention of all mass media of the world in recent years. In 2017, the high level of tourism demand in terms of cultural, social and economic indicators, overcrowding in some countries and geographic regions, and the massive anti-tourism protests in major cities and destinations related to conflicts between local residents and stakeholders of tourist areas. As a result of the extensive media coverage, a worldwide debate has begun on whether tourism should continue or not.

It is possible to examine both the positive and negative sides of these problems in one's actions that result from interactions between a person and another person, or between societies that show their different characters in different situations. The socio-psychological consequences of tourism, which are social events that results from mutual interactions between visitors and other tourists, locals or employees, and other people or groups of people can have both positive and negative effects in terms of social, psychological and social psychological.

It is the long-term permanent changes that occur in the behavior of the individual as a result of experiences (experience, education-training, observation) [4]. From that perspective we can include topics that are related to social psychology; group conformity behavior, persuasion, power, social influence, obedience, prejudice, reduction of prejudice, discrimination, stereotypes, social cognition, social perception, social categories, aggression, altruistic behaviors, interpersonal attraction, attitudes and attitude change, communication, impression making, small groups, leadership, mass behavior, and intergroup relations [5], and learning (Güney, 2009) Therefore, in the area where it occurs, tourism may contribute to the creation of the aforementioned social psychological problems among both individuals and groups. For instance, because of tourism, prejudiced communities from different backgrounds can get to know one another better and overcome their biases.

From long ago, our ancestors often used the phrase "one cannot be a Muslim until one is a foreigner". They were sure that this process can develop a person's spiritual maturity by experiencing different cultures, customs, worldviews, people with different natures and difficulties while travelling. From these processes, today's scientists analyze such changes in human behavior and nature through the transformational learning theory. The research of transformational learning in tourism recently supports the existence of social psychological effects of tourism. For example, Pitman et al. (2010) in the research on transformational learning in educational tourism; educational tourism has been found to be characterized by intentional and

structured learning experiences that provide opportunities for the teacher to immerse himself in experiences that have the potential to challenge previously held beliefs and prejudices. Coghlan & Gooch [6] reconceptualized volunteer tourism as a form of transformative learning in which all participants (including members of the host community) learn and change as a result of their experience and trials.

CONCLUSION

Although the tourism sector today is considered a separate education and service sector, its success depends on many factors; including economic trends, social rules, cultural differences, natural phenomena, and psychological laws. From this point of view, the socio-psychological impact of tourism includes many positive and negative processes. The process of transformational learning is one of the widely discussed effects of how much human behavior, nature, and experiences are acquired during travels. Today, the impact of tourism from a social and psychological point of view is one of the most important features. Such a feature can serve as the main source of resources for tourists' advertising or promotion of these tourist attractions, as well as conclusions about the return visits of tourists to tourist attractions.

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